

CHEMICAL AND MEDICINAL SIGNIFICANCE OF PYRAZOLE

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ANNOTATION

This article analyzes various chemical and medical issues facing chemistry, the importance of organic chemistry in the people and agriculture, pyrazole, which is widely used in industry and medicine, its structure, general and specific properties.

Key words: organic chemistry, natural agent, pyrazole, acetylene, diazomethane, alanine, analgin, fenpyroximate, celecoxib, hydrazine.

АБСТРАКТНЫЙ

В данной статье анализируются проблемы, стоящие перед наукой химией, значение органической химии в народном хозяйстве, пиразол, который широко применяется в промышленности и медицине, его строение, общие и специфические свойства. Ключевые слова: органическая химия, природные свойства, пиразол, ацетилен, диазометан, аланин, фенпироксимат, целекоксиб, гидразин.

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INTRODUCTION

The renewal of production technologies, scientific discoveries and the direct transformation of technology into the production force require specialist personnel to independently and regularly deepen, update, supplement and expand

their knowledge. Learning chemistry with a special approach in higher and secondary special and public education on the basis of interactive and modern technologies has become the demand of the times. The Institute of Physics and Chemistry of Polymers of the Federal Republic of Uzbekistan (PFKI) is the leading scientific institution in Uzbekistan in the field of synthetic and natural polymers. PFKI scientists make a significant contribution to the development of fundamental and practical problems of the physics and chemistry of polymers. They solve scientific problems, such as synthesizing biologically active polymers for agriculture and medicine, obtaining polysaccharides that can be widely used in medicine, ecology, and pharmaceuticals through the method of chemical modification, and developing technology for extracting cellulose from cotton wool for various purposes. have made great progress. Pyrazole and its derivatives are considered very important in agriculture and medicine, and studying its structure is necessary for science.

REFERENCES AND METHODOLOGY

The term pyrazole was given to this class of compounds in 1883 by the German chemist Ludwig Knorr.[1] In 1898, pyrazole was synthesized from acetylene and diazomethane by the classical method developed by the German chemist Hans von Pechmann. In 1959, the first natural pyrazole 1-pyrazolyl-alanine was isolated from watermelon seeds.[2] Pyrazole derivatives are widely used in medicine[3]. The pyrazole ring is found in a variety of pesticides, including fungicides, insecticides, and herbicides, including fenpiroximate, fipronil, tebufenpyrad, and tolfenpyrad. Pyrazole moieties are listed by the US FDA as one of the most commonly used ring systems for small molecule drugs. Pyrazole is an organic compound with the formula $C_3H_3N_2$, which is a heterocycle characterized by a 5-membered ring of three carbon atoms and two adjacent nitrogen atoms[4]. Pyrazole is a weak base, pK_b is equal to 11.5 (2.49

pK_a of the conjugated acid at 25°C). [2] Pyrazoles are also a class of compounds that have a C_3N_2 ring with adjacent nitrogen atoms. [3] Well-known drugs containing a pyrazole ring are celecoxib (Celebrex) and the anabolic steroid stanozolol. In pyrazole, a closed 1-electron sextet is formed due to one electron of three carbon atoms and three electrons of two nitrogen atoms. Therefore, these heterocycles exhibit aromatic properties. Looking at the structural formulas of pyrazole and imidazole, one of the nitrogen atoms in their ring is similar to the nitrogen atom of pyridine, and the other is similar to the nitrogen atom of pyrrole. In this structure, 3- and 5-substituted pyrazoles, as well as 4- and 5-substituted imidazoles must be present. But the mobile hydrogen atom in pyrazole and imidazole is from one nitrogen atom. In both pyrazole and imidazole, electrophilic exchange takes place in the 4th position of the ring. Such isomers are not formed due to rapid transition to another. Both nitrogen atoms in pyrazole and imidazole molecules are of equal value. Therefore, the 4- and 5-states of 3- and 5-imidazole in pyrazole are practically indistinguishable from each other. Therefore, the substitution at the 3- and 5-carbon atoms of pyrazole is designated as 3(5)- or 5(3)- substitution, and the substitution at the 4- and 5-positions of imidazole is designated as 4(5)- or 5(4)- substitution:

These medicinal substances are white or yellowish-white crystalline powder, antipyrine and analgin are easily soluble in water, butadione is insoluble. Butadione is soluble in alkaline solutions and chloroform. Analgin decomposes under the influence of moisture

Uses: Pain reliever, anti-cold and antipyretic. Storage. It is stored according to the B-list.

CONCLUSION Heterocyclic compounds are among organic substances and are widely distributed in nature and widely used in industry. Currently, more than 60% of the most important and widely used drugs are heterocyclic compounds. The presence of various heteroatoms in the ring causes the

substance to exhibit specific chemical properties. Pyrazole, like pyrrole, is a weak base and a weak acid at the same time. Pyrazole is a colorless crystal. In contrast to pyrrole, it clearly expresses the basicity in relationships with the presence of the 2nd nitrogen atom. Pyrazole has the property of aromaticity, it is sulfonated and nitrated more easily than thiophene. Pyrazole boils at 69-70 C, smells like pyridine, dissolves well in water, alcohol, ether and benzene. We see that alkylation, acylation, nitration, sulfonation, and halogenation reactions are characteristic of electrophilic exchange reactions for pyrazole. The condensed system of benzene and pyrazole rings - indazole - is less studied than benzimidazole, and only recently has the interest of chemists in this compound increased significantly. Indazole is not found in natural substances.

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